

Press Release Set 2023

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators celebrates a year of joint work on strategies in Science in Hungary

On the 5th and 6th of October 2023, the six founding countries of the European University E³UDRES² will meet at the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, in Hungary, to celebrate and discuss the first year of joint work within the scope of the project E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators.

This event marks a year of collaborative efforts to develop joint research and innovation strategies. Among the objectives of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is the co-creation of a common strategy and agenda to accelerate the transformation of the region into a European Research and Innovation Center for Smart and Sustainable Regions. Furthermore, the project aims to develop structured support programs aimed at enabling scientific communities to fully embrace Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Engaged Science and Engaged Education.

One of the main focuses of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is to achieve equitable conditions in terms of institutional Human Resources for Research strategies and policies. This involves addressing significant challenges, such as implementing new career assessments and joint recruitment strategies.

Another crucial goal is the development of a structured and integrated framework to harmoniously connect all Research and Innovation ecosystems and the knowledge triangle of the E³UDRES² alliance, which encompasses education, research and innovation. The project actively promotes dialogue with other similar alliances, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), HEI associations and political decision-makers.

With an innovative and collaborative approach, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project aims to transform the region into a hub of excellence in Research and Innovation. This initiative aims to create a sustainable and smart future for all European citizens.

The project is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe program (Project No 101071317). For more information about the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project visit <https://www.entrenovators.eu/>.

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EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

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